

BIOPSYCHOSOCIAL HEALTH STATUS OF A STATE UNIVERSITY FACULTY MEMBERS, REGION IV-A, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the current biological, psychological and social support status of a state university faculty members in relation to their health. Specifically, it assessed respondents' general health; biological, psychological and perceived interpersonal social support status; determined differences in responses among four variables when grouped according to profile; tested relationships existing among the variables of the study and proposed a physical and mental health intervention program. The study employed mixed methods using the sequential explanatory design. Data were gathered from 242 faculty members coming from 10 campuses of the state university in which validated and standardized questionnaires were utilized. From the gathered data, weighted mean, frequency, percentage, chi-square, ANOVA and Pearson Chi-square were used. Results revealed that majority of respondents were hypertensive, have medical history of hypertension, have genetic predisposition to hypertension and are not taking maintenance drugs. In addition, depression, anxiety and stress is generally mild; with average levels of irrational beliefs and perceived interpersonal social support. Significant difference in responses were found in terms of general health in relation to biological and psychological statuses and perceived interpersonal social support when grouped according to profile variables. Moreover, significant relationship was established between family history of chronic illnesses, impairment and anxiety; stroke and depression; heart disease and emotional irresponsibility; diabetes and emotional irresponsibility; kidney disease and rigidity; autoimmune disorder and emotional irresponsibility as well as impairment and tangible social support; heart disease and appraisal; stroke and belongingness. Lastly, an intervention program was proposed to promote physical and mental health status of the respondents.

Keywords: health, biopsychosocial model, chronic illnesses, sequential explanatory mixed methods, Philippines